

Table S1 Instrumental parameters of the SF-ICP-MS used in this work.

Instrument	ELEMENT2 Thermo Finnigan
Forward power	1,350 W
Reflected power	< 2 W
Nebuliser	Concentric
Solution uptake rate	0.4 mL min ⁻¹ (pumped)
Spray chamber	Cyclonic
Sampling and skimmer cones	Ni (Thermo Finnigan)
Sample gas flow	1 to 1.5 L min ⁻¹
Cool argon flow rate	16 L min ⁻¹
Auxiliary argon flow rate	1.0 L min ⁻¹
Torch	Capacitive decoupling Pt shield torch
RF frequency	27.12 Mhz
Sensitivity	1 x 10 ⁶ cps per 1 ng mL ⁻¹ ¹¹⁵ In (in Low Resolution)
Autosampler	ESI SC 3 Fast
Take-up time	15 s
Wash time	10 s
Number of acquisition	6 (3 runs and 2 pass)
Mass window LR	150% for each isotope
Search window LR	150% for each isotope
Samples per peak LR	20
Integration window LR	80% for each isotope
Mass window HR	As75 65%, In115 125%
Search window HR	60%
Samples per peak HR	30
Integration window HR	60%
Scan type	E scan for each isotope
Integration type	Average for each isotope

Table S2 Tukey's post-hoc test matrices declaring the significant differences between variants of elution agents on the level of significance $\alpha=0.05$.**As**

Variant	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
A		0.002742	0.003433	0.000145	0.000145	0.004319	0.000145
B	0.002742		1.000000	0.000145	0.000147	0.999997	0.000145
C	0.003433	1.000000		0.000145	0.000147	1.000000	0.000145
D	0.000145	0.000145	0.000145		0.998790	0.000145	1.000000
E	0.000145	0.000147	0.000147	0.998790		0.000146	0.995636
F	0.004319	0.999997	1.000000	0.000145	0.000146		0.000145
G	0.000145	0.000145	0.000145	1.000000	0.995636	0.000145	

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Variant	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
A		0.000000	0.129296	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.001182
B	0.000000		0.000004	0.000000	0.000172	0.000099	0.000685
C	0.129296	0.000004		0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.561430
D	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000		0.000066	0.000115	0.000000
E	0.000000	0.000172	0.000000	0.000066		0.999996	0.000000
F	0.000000	0.000099	0.000000	0.000115	0.999996		0.000000
G	0.001182	0.000685	0.561430	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	

Fig. S1 Box plots showing significant differences between elution variants expressed as mean, standard deviation, and mean $\pm 1.96 \times$ SD.